

MODULATORY EFFECTS OF *PROSOPIS CINERARIA* EXTRACTS ON MILK ACUTE PHASE PROTEINS IN *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* INDUCED SUBCLINICAL MASTITIS IN CATTLE

M.M. Meena^{1*}, Disha Sanwal², Sonali Sehrawat³, Anshu Singh³, Dilip Singh Meena², SR Gupta⁴ and J.P. Kachhawa^{4*}

Department of Veterinary Medicine, College of Veterinary and Animal Science, Rajasthan University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Bikaner-334 001, Rajasthan, India

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was planned to analysis of acute phase proteins viz. Haptoglobin (Hp) and milk amyloid A (MAA) resulted due to *Staphylococcus aureus* associated subclinical mastitis (SCM) and to know the effect of therapy of extract of leaves of *Prosopis cineraria* on these acute phase proteins. For the present investigation 12 sub-clinical mastitic cattle were selected and divided randomly in 2 groups (Group II and Group III) for therapeutic study. The mean±SE values of MAA and Hp in SCM affected pre-treatment Groups II and Group III were significantly higher (P<0.05) as compared to control Group and decreased after the receiving of the treatment.

Keywords: Acute phase proteins, milk amyloid A, *Prosopis cineraria*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, subclinical mastitis.

Introduction

Subclinical mastitis still remains to be a herd problem, without considerable clinical signs and gross changes in milk. Variable prevalence of SCM was reported by many researcher at different geographical location 29% by Plozza *et al.* (2011), 49.78 per cent by Kachhawa *et al.* (2019) and 59.43% by Bhat *et al.* (2016). The major isolated bacterial pathogens responsible for bovine mastitis are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* and *Streptococcus uberis* (Bramley *et al.*, 1996; Riffon *et al.*, 2001). Out of them *Staphylococcus aureus* is found to be the chief organism and most contributing contagious bacterial pathogen in subclinical mastitis (Kachhawa *et al.*, 2019; Riffon *et al.*, 2001; Jena *et al.*, 2015). An acute phase response (APR) results in an increase in systemic and local concentrations of acute-phase proteins (APP). Two of those proteins, haptoglobin (Hp) and milk amyloid A, play a significant role in the early response of the mammary gland to pathogenic bacteria (Eckersall *et al.*, 2001). There is paucity of literature on herbal plant extract and its effect on biomarker proteins i.e. APPs. Hence, it is dire need of hour to investigate the herbal plant extract on sub-clinical mastitis and counsel suitable therapeutic plan. Keeping this in mind, the present study was conducted to assess the effect of *Prosopis cineraria* (khejri) extract on acute phase proteins in milk due to *Staphylococcus aureus* associated subclinical mastitis in cattle.

Materials and Methods

Ethical statement

The present research work was carried out with the approval taken from Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of College of Veterinary and Animal Science, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India. The samples were collected from the animals as per standard sample collection procedure with due care of animals

without giving any stress and harm to the animals.

Animals

For the present study milk samples of 339 quarters of 86 cows were collected and screened by California mastitis test (CMT). The CMT positive samples further subjected to the laboratory for somatic cell count (SCC), electrical conductivity, cultural examination and APPs analysis. Only those animals were included in this study who had SCC count more than 500000 per ml and positive for *Staphylococcus aureus*. Therefore, 12 sub-clinical mastitic cattle were selected for therapeutic trial and divided randomly in 2 groups (6 in each group) viz. Group II and Group III. Further, 6 apparently healthy cows were selected as control and kept in Group I who were found to be negative for subclinical mastitis by CMT, cultural examination and having SCC less than 200000 per ml.

Sample collection

The milk samples were collected under strict hygienic condition. The udder and teats were washed and wiped with 70% alcohol swab. First three-four stripping of fore milk were discarded. Approximately 30 ml of fore milk from each teat was collected in sterilized tubes. All the samples were transported to the laboratory and kept in refrigeration (4°C) till analysis. Milk samples were collected from all 12 subclinical mastitis affected cows at 10 days interval taking first day as pre-treatment and 10th day as post-treatment. Milk samples collected from all 12 cows were then subjected for analysis of SCC and acute phase proteins (milk amyloid A and haptoglobin).

Estimation of MAA and Hp concentration in milk

The concentration of milk amyloid A (MAA) was determined in milk samples of different groups using commercially available sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

^{1*}Veterinary Officer, Department of Animal Husbandry, Government of Rajasthan; ²Ph.D. Scholar; ³M.V.Sc. Scholar; ⁴Assistant Professor and Corresponding author E mail address: jpkachhawa@gmail.com

(ELISA) kit (Tridelata Mast ID range MMA assay, Tridelata Development Ltd., Kildare, Ireland, Cat. No.: TP-807), and concentration of and Haptoglobin (Hp) was also estimated by sandwich ELISA kit (Bioassay Technology Laboratory, Shanghai, China, Cat. No.: E2263Bo). The procedures for ELISA kit were followed as per manufacturer's instructions.

Therapeutic study

The effect of aqueous and alcoholic extract of leaves of *Prosopis cineraria* on acute phase proteins was estimated. These groups were administered various therapeutic regimens as described below:-

Group I: Healthy cows were served as control.

Group II: Cows were administered oral aqueous extract of leaves of *Prosopis cineraria* @ 100 mg/kg body weight twice daily for 10 days.

Group III: Cows were administered oral alcoholic extract of leaves of *Prosopis cineraria* @ 100 mg/kg body weight twice daily for 10 days.

Statistical analysis

The data obtained in the research work were statistically analyzed and compared using standard formulas given for mean, standard error and one way analysis of variance (F-test) as per the procedures explained by Snedecor and Cochran (2004). Duncan's multiple range test was used to differentiate between significant means at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* associated mastitis

Milk samples of 86 cows having 339 functional quarters and 5 non-functional were tested by cow side California mastitis test. The results showed 94 (27.72% quarter-wise) functional quarters of 39 (45.35% cow-wise) cows were found to be positive for subclinical mastitis. Out of 94 functional quarters these 39 cows, 18 (19.14% quarter-wise) quarters of 16 (41.02% cow-wise) cows were found to be positive for subclinical mastitis by *Staphylococcus aureus* in cultural examination. Prior to the CMT carried out the animals were examined physically for clinical mastitis for exclusion. Most commonly observed clinical signs were udder swelling, redness, decreased milk production, pain on palpation, watery or flaky or curd like and abnormal colour of milk.

Many researchers reported *Staphylococcus aureus* is the most dominant bacteria responsible for higher prevalence of clinical and subclinical mastitis in cows (Jena *et al.*, 2015; Singh *et al.*, 2016). Harini and Sumathi (2011) recovered 58%, Savita (2016) reported 52.68% *Staphylococcus aureus* from lactating cows which were screened for sub clinical mastitis. Hamid *et al.* (2017) reported that *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most prevalent and contagious pathogen that was found in 30-40% of all mastitis cases. Kachhawa (2018) found that most commonly isolated bacteria from subclinical mastitic milk samples of cross bred cows of Bikaner city was *Staphylococcus aureus* (40.78%).

Staphylococcus aureus produces toxins that destroy cell membranes, directly damage milk-producing tissue, and induce necrosis in bovine mammary glands (Sordillo and Nickerson, 1988 and Trinidad *et al.*, 1990). *Staphylococcus aureus* is contagious in nature present in the udders of infected cows and also in cuts and chaps on the teat skin

colonizes teat skin, vagina, muzzle and other body sites, as well as bedding, feed stuffs, air and equipments thus increasing chances of infection to other cow (Guimaraes *et al.*, 2017).

California mastitis test

The CMT results of quarter milk samples of subclinical mastitis affected cows are presented in Table 1. In Group II, 8 quarters were found positive and in Group III, 7 quarters were found positive by CMT. In Group II out of 8 quarters, 6 quarters were distinct positive (++) and 2 quarters were strong positive(+++) while in Group III out of 7 quarters, one quarter was weak positive (+), 4 quarters were distinct positive (++) and 2 quarters were strong positive (+++). For detection of subclinical mastitis there are series of methods and tests, but the simplest and practically reliable method is California mastitis test (De Viegner *et al.*, 2005). Karimuribo *et al.* (2006) concluded that CMT was a superior screening diagnostic aid for detection of subclinical mastitis.

Table1: CMT results of milk samples of subclinical mastitis affected cows

Group II (8 quarters) Aqueous extract			Group III (7 quarters) Alcoholic extract		
Animal No.	SCM	CMT	Animal No.	SCM	CMT
I	LH	++	I	RH	+++
II	RH	++	II	LF	++
	RF	++		III	RH
III	LF	++	IV	LH	++
IV	RH	++	V	RH	++
V	RF	+++		RF	++
	VI	LF	+++	VI	LF
LH		++			

(+) indicates positive for CMT

According to Middleton *et al.* (2004) and Viguier *et al.* (2009) CMT is based on the principle that the addition of a detergent to a milk sample with a high cell count will lyse the cells, releases nucleic acids and other cellular constituents and lead to the formation of a 'gel-like' matrix consistency. Kachhawa *et al.* (2019) proposed CMT as a most useful diagnostic tool in the field conditions for detection of mastitis because it can be performed by any unskilled person and no need of laboratory facilities.

Acute phase proteins

The pre-treatment and post-treatment mean±SE values of MAA (µg/ml) and Haptoglobin (Hp) of quarter milk samples of healthy control and subclinical mastitis affected cows are presented in Table 2 and Figure 1 & 2.

Significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) pre-treatment mean±SE values of MAA were observed in SCM affected Group II and Group III when compared to control Group. The finding of present study was in accordance with the findings of Molenaar *et al.* (2009) and Jaeger *et al.* (2016). The mean±SE values of Group II and III were significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) after the treatment in comparison to their respective pre-treatment values but yet not reached near to the level of control value in both groups. Similarly, the pre-treatment mean±SE values of Hp in SCM affected Group II and Group III were significantly

Table 2: Pre- and post- treatment mean±SE values of MAA (µg/ml) andHp (ng/ml) of quarter milk samples of control and subclinical mastitis affected cows

Parameter	MAA (µg/ml)	Hp(ng/ml)	
Groups	Treatment	Mean±SE	
GroupI	(Control)	10.044 ^a ±0.267	7.319 ^a ±0.138
GroupII	Pre-treatment	30.511 ^d ±0.694	17.258 ^c ±0.471
	Post-treatment	21.709 ^c ±2.269	12.804 ^b ±1.234
GroupIII	Pre-treatment	30.787 ^d ±0.501	18.567 ^c ±0.585
	Post-treatment	16.749 ^b ±2.326	10.944 ^b ±1.062

Means with different superscripts in columns were differ significantly (P<0.05)

Figure 1: Pre- and post- treatment mean values of MAA of quarter milk samples of control and subclinical mastitis affected cows

Figure 2: Pre- and post- treatment mean values of Hp of quarter milk samples of control and subclinical mastitis affected cows

higher (P<0.05) as compared to control Group and post-treatment mean±SE values of Group II and III were significantly decreased (P<0.05) in comparison to their respective pre-treatment values. But as MAA the Hp level after treatment not reached near to the level of control value in both groups.

In the present study the isolated *Staphylococcus aureus* was accountable for subclinical mastitis in cows and responsible for the changes in the acute phase proteins (milk amyloid A and Haptoglobin) of milk. The acute phase proteins are believed to be the indicative biomarkers for the udder health although these are secreted in the blood from liver in response to the inflammatory processes triggered at the time of bacterial injury to the udder tissues (Petersen *et al.*, 2004). The

haptoglobin and amyloid A proteins secreted in bovine milk passively via the blood-milk-barrier due to increased permeability of udder tissues in mastitis (Eckersall *et al.*, 2001). Furthermore, the level of amyloid A and Haptoglobin in milk is started to increase within 12 hours after *Staphylococcus aureus* infection and reached its peak concentrations within three days (Eckersall *et al.*, 2006). However serum amyloid A locally produced as a particular isoform (M-SAA3) by bovine mammary epithelial cells. Serum amyloid A and M-SAA3 together are called milk amyloid A (MAA), which is measurable in milk samples. MAA has proven to be a reliable biomarker for both subclinical mastitis and clinical mastitis (Gerardi *et al.*, 2009 and Molenaar *et al.*, 2009). Thomas *et al.* (2015) stated that in dairy cattle, haptoglobin and a mammary-associated serum amyloid A, produced by the inflamed mammary gland during episodes of mastitis. The acute phase proteins (APP) such as haptoglobin (Hp), serum amyloid A and C-reactive protein (CRP) act as inflammatory biomarkers for mastitis in Cattle. Jaeger *et al.* (2016) suggested use of SCC and MAA-ELISA as a combined screening procedure for situations such as a *Staphylococcus aureus* control program. The formation of Hp-Hb complex decreases the freely available of the iron residues requires for bacterial growth therefore haptoglobin possess an antibacterial activity indirectly (Murata *et al.*, 2004). Narwane *et al.* (2014) and Kulshreshtha *et al.* (2019) established antimicrobial activity of *Prosopis cineraria* leaves against many bacterial pathogens. Their study revealed the presence of phyto constituents viz. tannins, saponins, sesquiterpene, alkaloids and flavonoids in the extract which is responsible for antimicrobial activity. Mittal *et al.* (2013) stated that *Prosopis cineraria* are being used traditionally for the treatment of various ailments like leprosy, dysentery, asthma, leucoderma, dyspepsia and ear ache etc. Various phytoconstituents like tannins, flavone derivatives and alkaloids have been isolated from the plant. Pharmacological activities like analgesic, antipyretic, antihyperglycemic, antihypercholesterolemic, antitumor have been reported from the plant extracts. In this study, MAA and Hp level in cows affected with SCM significantly decreased after treatment with extracts leaves of *Prosopis cineraria*. It indicated that after treatment the cows were reviving from infection. Also, Hp acts synergistically along with extracts leaves of *Prosopis cineraria* for elimination of infection.

Conclusion

The present study investigated the MAA and Hp in cows suffering from subclinical mastitis and treated by locally available plant *Prosopis cineraria* leaves aqueous and alcoholic extracts. On the basis of above findings, it was concluded that the study provides a strong evidence for the significance of MAA and Hp measurement in milk during SCM and can be used as a useful diagnostic tool. *In vivo* therapeutic studies showed that alcoholic extract of leaves of *Prosopis cineraria* can be used for therapy of SCM as an alternative medicine.

Conflict of interest

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest in the study.

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